

EFFECTIVENESS OF LITERACY-INTEGRATED MATH LESSON SCRIPTS ON STUDENTS' MATHEMATICS ACHIEVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the mathematics achievement of students using Literacy-Integrated Math (LIM) lesson scripts. Specifically, it aimed to determine the level of mathematics achievement of students exposed and not exposed to the LIM lesson scripts and to test whether a significant difference existed between the two groups. A quasi-experimental research design was employed in a public secondary school in Maramag, Bukidnon, Philippines, involving Grade 7 students assigned to experimental and control groups. One group was exposed to the LIM lesson scripts, while the other group was exposed to non-LIM instruction. The LIM lesson scripts were developed based on the results of the Rapid Mathematics Assessment and aligned with the Revised K to 10 Curriculum and the ARAL Program. Data were gathered using a researcher-made mathematics pretest and posttest, and achievement levels were described using mean, frequency, and percentages. The data were analyzed using frequency, percentage, mean, and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at the 0.05 level of significance. Results revealed that both groups had comparable pretest achievement; however, after the intervention, the LIM group obtained a higher posttest mean score of 33.70 compared with 28.02 for the non-LIM group. ANCOVA further showed a significant difference in posttest mathematics achievement between the two groups after controlling for pretest scores, with a significant group effect, $p < .001$, and a moderate effect size (partial $\eta^2 = .133$). The findings indicate that LIM lesson scripts effectively enhance students' mathematics achievement.

Keywords: *mathematics achievement, literacy-integrated math, lesson scripts, mathematics instruction, quasi-experimental design*

INTRODUCTION

Students' low achievement in mathematics remains a persistent concern in Philippine education. Many learners struggle to understand mathematical concepts not only because of the abstract nature of the subject but also because of weak foundational knowledge and limited reading comprehension skills. In mathematics, learners are expected to interpret instructions, understand mathematical vocabulary, and make sense of worded and contextualized problems before applying operations and procedures. When these literacy demands are not adequately addressed, students experience difficulty in constructing meaning from mathematical tasks, which in turn contributes to poor academic performance. Thus, mathematics achievement is influenced not only by numeracy skills but also by learners' ability to comprehend and process language in mathematical contexts.

The seriousness of this concern is reflected in both international and national assessment results. In the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment, the Philippines ranked second to the last in mathematics among 79 participating countries, and in the 2022 cycle, it ranked fifth to the last among 81 participating countries (OECD, 2019; OECD, 2023). Similarly, in the 2019 Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study, Filipino learners ranked lowest in Grade 4 mathematics among 58 countries (IEA, 2019). At the national level, results of the National Achievement Test have likewise shown that students' mathematics performance has remained below the expected mastery level, indicating continuing learning gaps in the subject. These findings suggest that mathematics instruction must respond more directly to the factors that hinder learners' understanding and performance.

This concern is also evident in the local context. In Bukidnon, mathematics performance in the National Achievement Test has remained low, reflecting the continuing challenge of improving learners' academic achievement in the subject. Reports from the Division of Bukidnon further show that junior high school learners have demonstrated weak performance in mathematics, particularly in tasks that require comprehension and interpretation. These outcomes emphasize the need for instructional interventions that are responsive to learners' actual needs and grounded in the realities of classroom instruction. More importantly, they support the direction of current educational plans that prioritize the strengthening of literacy and numeracy skills among learners.

Several studies have identified poor foundational skills as one of the major factors associated with low mathematics performance (Fung et al., 2018; Maamin et al., 2022). However, an important but often overlooked dimension of this difficulty is learners' inability to comprehend written mathematical tasks. Mathematics problems, especially at the secondary level, are often text-rich and require students to decode, interpret, and analyze

information before arriving at a solution. In this sense, reading and mathematical literacy are interdependent. Knighten (2025) emphasized the importance of integrating literacy skills into mathematics instruction, while Bernardo (2022) found a positive relationship between students' reading proficiency and mathematics achievement. Likewise, Hassinger et al. (2015) and Riccomini (2015) noted that the integration of reading strategies, vocabulary development, and comprehension support in mathematics can strengthen learners' understanding of concepts and improve their academic performance.

One instructional response to this need is the development of Literacy-Integrated Math lesson scripts. LIM lesson scripts are contextualized instructional materials designed to embed literacy processes into mathematics teaching in order to strengthen learners' comprehension, interpretation, and problem-solving skills. By incorporating guided reading, contextualized examples, vocabulary support, and structured comprehension tasks into mathematics lessons, these materials help learners make sense of mathematical language and connect ideas more meaningfully. In this way, LIM lesson scripts provide an approach that addresses not only the computational demands of mathematics but also the literacy demands embedded in the subject. Such integration is especially relevant in classrooms where students experience difficulty with text-based and comprehension-oriented mathematical tasks.

Despite the recognized importance of literacy integration in mathematics, limited empirical studies in the Philippine secondary school context have focused on the development and use of localized, curriculum-aligned, and teacher-friendly instructional materials specifically designed for this purpose. Most available studies have examined general reading interventions or other instructional strategies without concentrating on literacy-integrated materials in mathematics. This gap highlights the need for the development and evaluation of instructional resources that directly address learners' reading-related difficulties in mathematics. Hence, this study was conducted to develop, evaluate, and determine the effectiveness of Literacy-Integrated Math lesson scripts on students' mathematics achievement.

Research Questions

The study aimed to investigate the students' mathematics achievement using Literacy-Integrated Math (LIM) lesson scripts. Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the level of students' achievement in mathematics when exposed to literacy-integrated math lesson scripts (LIM) and non-literacy-integrated math lesson scripts (non-LIM) in pretest and posttest scores?
2. Is there a significant difference in the level of students' mathematics achievement between those exposed and those not exposed to the Literacy-Integrated Math lesson scripts?

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in a public secondary school in Maramag, Bukidnon, Philippines. A quasi-experimental research design was employed, involving an experimental group exposed to the Literacy-Integrated Math (LIM) lesson scripts and a control group exposed to non-Literacy-Integrated Math (non-LIM) instruction. The participants were selected through the total enumeration of two intact Grade 7 sections. The investigation was limited to determining the effect of the LIM lesson scripts on students' mathematics achievement during the implementation period.

Data were gathered using a researcher-made mathematics pretest and posttest, which were used to assess students' mathematics achievement before and after the implementation of the instructional intervention. The test was developed based on the third quarter competencies in Grade 7 Mathematics and was subjected to validity and reliability testing prior to administration. The level of achievement was interpreted using the proficiency scale adapted from Department of Education Order No. 8, s. 2015, otherwise known as the Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program. This consisted of 53 items aligned with a Table of Specification based on the HOTS-SOLO Taxonomy, validated by six mathematics experts with CVI of 1.00, and pilot-tested on thirty-five Grade 8 students from a nearby secondary school with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.791. Students' performance was interpreted using the following scale adapted from DepEd (2015):

Score	Percentage Score	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
48–53	90 – 100	Advance	Outstanding
43–47	85 – 89	Proficient	Very Satisfactory
38–42	80 – 84	Approaching Proficiency	Satisfactory
33–37	75 – 79	Developing	Fairly Satisfactory
0–32	74 and below	Beginning	Did not meet expectations

The data gathering procedure involved administering the pretest to both groups before the implementation of the intervention and the posttest after the implementation period. Collected data were organized, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted using appropriate statistical tools. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, and mean were used to determine the level of students' mathematics achievement. To test whether a significant difference existed in mathematics achievement between the group exposed to the Literacy-Integrated Math lesson scripts and the group exposed to non-Literacy-Integrated Math instruction, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was employed. All statistical analyses were performed at the 0.05 level of significance. The study was limited to the variables included in the investigation and to the assessment of mathematics achievement as measured by the researcher-made test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Students' Mathematics Achievement

Table 1. Students' Level in Mathematics Achievement when Exposed to Literacy-Integrated Math Lesson Scripts (LIM) and non-Literacy Integrated Math Lesson Script in Pretest and Posttest Scores

Raw Score	RANGE	LIM LESSON SCRIPT GROUP (Experimental Group)				NON-LIM LESSON SCRIPT GROUP (Control Group)				Qualitative Interpretation
		Pretest		Posttest		Pretest		Posttest		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
48–53	90 – 100	0	0%	1	2.17%	0	0%	0	0%	O
43–47	85 – 89.9	0	0%	3	6.52%	0	0%	1	2.17%	VS
38–42	80 – 84.9	0	0%	10	21.74%	0	0%	0	0%	S
33–37	75 – 79.9	0	0%	11	23.91%	0	0%	7	15.22%	FS
0–32	74 and below	46	100%	21	46.65%	46	100%	38	82.61%	DNME
	Total Mean Score	46	100%	46	100%	46	100%	46	100%	
			18.85		33.70		16.65		28.02	
	Overall MPS		35.57%		63.58%		31.42%		52.87%	

Legend: 90-100-Outstanding (O); 85-89 Very satisfactory (VS); 80-84 Satisfactory (S); 75-79 Fairly Satisfactory (FS); Below 75 Did not Meet Expectation (DNME)

Table 1 presents the students' level of mathematics achievement when exposed to the Literacy-Integrated Math (LIM) lesson scripts and non-Literacy-Integrated Math lesson scripts in terms of pretest and posttest scores. In the pretest, both the LIM group and the non-LIM group had all forty-six students, or one hundred percent, under the Did Not Meet Expectations (DNME) level. In the posttest, the LIM group showed improvement, with one student or 2.17% reaching Outstanding, three students or 6.52% in Very Satisfactory, ten students or 21.74% in Satisfactory, and eleven students or 23.91% in Fairly Satisfactory, while twenty-one students or 46.65% remained in Did Not Meet Expectations. In contrast, the non-LIM group posted one student or 2.17% in Very Satisfactory, seven students or 15.22% in Fairly Satisfactory, and thirty-eight students or 82.61% remained in Did Not Meet Expectations. The LIM group obtained a mean score of 18.85 in the pretest and 33.70 in the posttest, with an overall Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of 35.57% and 63.58%, respectively. The non-LIM group obtained a mean score

of 16.65 in the pretest and 28.02 in the posttest, with an overall MPS of 31.42% and 52.87%.

The data show that both groups improved after the intervention, but the improvement was greater in the LIM group. From pretest to posttest, the LIM group increased by 14.85 points in mean score and 28.01 percentage points in MPS, whereas the non-LIM group increased by 11.37 points in mean score and 21.45 percentage points in MPS. Moreover, more students in the LIM group moved into higher proficiency levels compared with those in the non-LIM group. These results indicate that the LIM lesson scripts were more effective than the non-LIM lesson scripts in improving students' mathematics achievement. Although both groups started at the same low performance level, the LIM group demonstrated a stronger upward movement in both mean score and proficiency distribution. This suggests that the integration of literacy processes into mathematics instruction contributed to better understanding and performance in mathematics.

In addition, the LIM approach appears to support deeper conceptual understanding and reading-based problem solving, enabling students to interpret and analyze contextualized mathematical tasks more effectively. This interpretation is consistent with research indicating that literacy integration in mathematics enhances comprehension of real-world problems and promotes higher-order reasoning (Ríos & Deng, 2020). Conversely, while structured repetition and modeling are effective for developing procedural competence, they may not sufficiently address comprehension-based challenges inherent in text-rich and non-routine mathematical tasks (NCTM, 2018).

Empirical studies further demonstrate that reading comprehension significantly predicts performance in mathematical problem-solving, particularly in tasks requiring interpretation and multi-step reasoning (Ríos & Deng, 2020). The Philippine National Report on PISA 2018 highlighted persistent weaknesses among Filipino learners in mathematical literacy, particularly in contextualized and higher-order tasks (Department of Education [DepEd], 2019). Subsequent analyses of Philippine data indicate that students demonstrate relative familiarity with procedural exercises but encounter difficulty when mathematical problems require integration of reading comprehension and analytical reasoning (Bernardo & Ismail, 2021).

Moreover, Philippine-based studies have further established that structured modeling and repetitive practice remain effective in developing procedural fluency and gradual mastery of mathematical skills (Magno, 2017; Bernardo, 2020). However, these approaches alone may not sufficiently address comprehension-based challenges inherent in text-dense and scenario-driven problems. Post-pandemic educational analyses also emphasize the need for integrated instructional strategies that simultaneously rebuild foundational skills and strengthen higher-order reasoning competencies disrupted by learning interruptions (UNESCO, 2021; World Bank, 2022).

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on Students' Mathematics Achievement

Table 2. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on Students' Mathematics Achievement when Exposed to LIM Lesson Scripts and Non-LIM Lesson Scripts

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
LIM	46	33.6957	7.04232
Non-LIM	46	28.0217	4.64514
Total	92	30.8587	6.58266

Source	SS	Df	MS	F-value	Sig.	Partial eta squared
Model	1143.437 ^a	2	571.719	18.174	.000	
Pretest (Covariate)	402.992	1	402.992	12.811	.001	0.126
Group	428.106	1	428.106	13.609	.000	0.133
Error	2799.726	89	31.458			
Total	91551.000	92				

Table 15 presents the results of the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) conducted to determine whether a significant difference exists in students' mathematics achievement between those exposed to Literacy-Integrated Math (LIM) lesson scripts and those exposed to non-LIM lesson scripts after pretest performance.

The overall ANCOVA model was statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.000, indicating that the combined predictors significantly explained the variance in students' posttest scores. The pretest covariate was likewise significant, with a p-value of 0.001, confirming that students' baseline performance had a significant influence on their posttest outcomes. More importantly, the instructional group effect remained significant even after controlling for pretest scores, with a p-value of 0.000 and a partial eta squared of .133, indicating a moderate effect size. The adjusted mean scores further show that the LIM group with a mean of 33.6957 outperformed the non-LIM group with a mean of 28.0217. These findings suggest that the superiority of the LIM group in the posttest cannot be explained solely by students' initial proficiency level. Although prior knowledge significantly predicted achievement, the literacy-integrated mathematics instruction contributed additional and meaningful improvement beyond what could be accounted for by baseline differences alone.

Moreover, the ANCOVA results indicate that even after statistically adjusting for prior achievement, students exposed to LIM instruction performed significantly better than those exposed to non-LIM instruction. The moderate effect size (partial $\eta^2 = .133$) suggests that the literacy-integrated approach had a meaningful instructional impact on students' mathematics achievement. This difference likely reflects variations in the type and depth of cognitive scaffolding provided by the two approaches. LIM instruction appears to have enhanced students' ability to read, decode, interpret, and reason through

contextualized mathematical tasks. Through reading passages and literacy-based activities, students were not only taught how to solve problems but were also helped to understand what the problem means, what information is important, and how mathematical reasoning can be applied in context. In contrast, non-LIM instruction strengthened procedural skills through teacher explanation, modeling, and repetition, but may not have fully addressed the comprehension-based demands of mathematical problem solving.

This finding is supported by mathematical literacy frameworks, which emphasize that comprehension, interpretation, and reasoning are essential competencies in solving real-world mathematical problems (OECD, 2022). Studies have shown that integrating reading strategies into mathematics instruction improves students' ability to analyze text-rich tasks and enhances overall problem-solving performance (Schleppwegrell, 2018; Ríos & Deng, 2020). These scholarly insights are consistent with the experiences shared by LIM respondents, who described improved understanding through reading passages and contextualized lesson delivery. In the Philippine context, the PISA 2018 National Report highlighted that Filipino learners struggle significantly with contextualized and higher-order mathematical tasks, particularly those requiring interpretation of written scenarios (DepEd, 2019). Subsequent analyses further emphasize that strengthening mathematical literacy through comprehension-focused instruction is necessary to address systemic learning gaps (Bernardo & Ismail, 2021).

Moreover, Philippine classroom-based studies have shown that contextualized and intervention-based mathematics materials can improve academic performance more effectively than traditional approaches, particularly when instruction integrates comprehension and real-life application (Magno, 2017; Bernardo, 2020). These findings closely align with the qualitative themes expressed by the LIM respondents and reinforce the statistical evidence showing improved achievement among students exposed to LIM lesson scripts. Overall, the results imply that the strength of LIM instruction lies not only in improving procedural performance, but more importantly in fostering conceptual understanding, contextual reasoning, and meaning-centered learning experiences that translate into higher mathematics achievement.

Conclusions

The results revealed that students exposed to the Literacy-Integrated Math (LIM) lesson scripts demonstrated higher mathematics achievement than those in the non-LIM group. Although both groups had comparable pretest results, the LIM group achieved a higher Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of 63.58, whereas the non-LIM group obtained a lower MPS of 52.87. Similarly, the LIM group obtained a higher posttest mean score of 33.70 compared with 28.02 for the non-LIM group. These findings suggest that the integration of literacy processes into mathematics instruction contributes to better learning outcomes in mathematics.

The Literacy-Integrated Math lesson scripts produced a statistically significant effect on students' mathematics achievement relative to non-LIM instruction. ANCOVA

findings indicated that the LIM group obtained a significantly higher posttest mathematics achievement score, with a mean of 33.6957, than the non-LIM group, which obtained a mean of 28.0217. A significant group effect was observed, $F = 13.609$, $p < .001$, with a moderate effect size (partial $\eta^2 = .133$). In addition, pretest achievement was a significant covariate, confirming that students' baseline performance influenced their posttest scores. However, even after controlling for pretest differences, the LIM group still performed significantly better than the non-LIM group. This indicates that integrating literacy processes into mathematics instruction can significantly enhance students' mathematics achievement by improving their understanding of mathematical language, interpretation of problems, and performance in contextualized tasks.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed for teachers, school administrators, curriculum planners, and future researchers.

It is recommended that mathematics teachers and instructional leaders integrate literacy-based and contextualized learning activities into mathematics instruction to improve students' mathematics achievement. School administrators and curriculum planners may support the wider use, monitoring, and possible adoption of Literacy-Integrated Math lesson scripts in junior high school mathematics classes to help address learners' difficulties in comprehension-based and text-rich mathematical tasks. In addition, the developed lesson scripts may be considered as supplementary instructional materials in implementing classroom interventions aligned with the goals of the ARAL Program and other literacy and numeracy recovery efforts. Future researchers may also conduct similar studies using larger samples, longer intervention periods, other grade levels, and additional mathematics competencies to further validate and extend the effectiveness of the Literacy-Integrated Math lesson scripts.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors affirm that ethical standards were observed throughout the conduct of the study. Informed consent was obtained from all participants and from parents or guardians when necessary after they were informed of the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, and their rights as participants, including the right to withdraw at any point without penalty. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained by withholding all identifying information from the research records and reports. The researchers likewise ensured that the welfare of the participants was protected throughout the implementation of the study. The authors further declare that no conflict of interest influenced the conduct or results of the research. All sources were properly acknowledged, plagiarism was strictly avoided, and the findings were interpreted objectively and used solely for academic and research purposes.

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